

The Arguments of Value: Notes for a Semiotics of Marketing

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1. The Marketing-Object

The encounter with marketing compels semiotics to confront a body of knowledge in a state of pre-theorization and to begin analysis of an object that is not clearly defined, though already widely explored. While marketing theory laments the absence of a general theory and a descriptive language adequate to its object, it has nonetheless developed procedures of discovery and generalization. The inductive method, followed by the identification of constants and hypotheses of regularity, has allowed for the formulation of specific laws that, however, have not fulfilled the demand for simplicity and generality.

On the contrary, a deductive procedure has predominantly characterized the semiotic approach to the marketing object: progressing from general properties of signification processes, semiotics seeks to deduce specific characteristics of marketing phenomena. This deductive approach is justified not so much by the limited or indeterminate nature of the object, but rather by the favorable circumstance that semiotic theory possesses a descriptive language intuitively adequate, at least in an initial phase, for the marketing object.

This object presents itself as a process of value exchange, where goods are invested with value—a process that presupposes a prior interpretive and evaluative act. The object that Marketing Theory is called upon to describe is therefore a semiotic process: no exchange can occur unless someone chooses to interpret the good as a sign of something. In other words, no exchange exists without semiosis.

However, for the exchange to occur, a mere act of cognitive interpretation is not sufficient: the virtualization of values, grasped as pure difference, must be followed by an act of value attribution. What is at stake, therefore, is not the semiotic character of the exchange process, but the criteria of value judgment, or the modes by which value is assigned. And it is on this theme that various schools of economic thought have long debated.

Even the opposition between subjective theories of the neo-classicists and objective theories of the neo-Ricardians, to mention a relatively recent form of this controversy, has in fact not reached a resolution: the theory of value remains an open question. While economic theory appears able to develop an autonomous theory of prices, it does not seem that a theory of marketing can do without a clearly defined theory of value.

Furthermore, neither absolute value theories, in their various formulations, nor theories based on utility functions or mathematical orderings of rational preference decisions,

adequately account for the complex process that precedes exchange.

We believe it is precisely the need for a new outlook, one that allows for the integration of labor-value theses, utility-value approaches, and others that also consider factors like scarcity, into a coherent theoretical framework, that calls for the contribution of semiotics.

For now, however, many authors remain anchored to pseudo-materialist premises, seeing in every direction imprecise “dematerializations” and “evaporations” of the object’s truths: its functionality, its concrete “use value,” its physicality—all reduced to “pure exchange value” by an uncontainable symbolic force. The implicit tendency to merge oppositions such as “materiality/immateriality,” “use value/exchange value,” “functionality/symbolicity” is a sign of confusion that is not merely terminological.

As referential fallacies and theories of needs reemerge, increasing reference is made to post-industrial culture as the cause of the “transformation of the commodity into a sign,” as if an object and its “use value”—understood here as its virtual functions—were not already linked through sign function, and as if the exchange of goods did not already require a process of symbolization. (cf. Eco, 1975: 40)

2. Pertinences

If exchange presupposes an act of value attribution, this latter necessarily implies an act of cognitive interpretation. Even before being posed in terms of evaluation, the issue of value must be addressed in terms of pertinence.

Marketing thought has always felt the operational need to distinguish between two problems: the one concerning the interpretation and positioning of a good, and the one concerning its value. Yet, the task of marketing theory today is to account for the ways in which descriptive values, purely positional or already endowed with a thymic connotation (Greimas, 1983: 97), and thus axiologized, are modalized through value judgments.

In other words, it is a matter of investigating the reciprocal influence that links value attribution and the traits rendered pertinent by interpretation.

3. Value

The investment of value is, in theory, independent from both the virtualization and the axiologization of a semic unit. The modal structure of the subject-of-state re-categorizes the value systems it assumes, modalizing axiological values into desirable or non-desirable ones (Greimas, 1983: 97–98).

However, value judgment takes place within a semantic space already shaped by the cognitive act. The hypothetical and interpretative nature of knowledge implies the actualization of certain content features—that is, a choice of pertinence which becomes the regulatory criterion of the evaluative path.

The practice on which pertinence depends is, in the case of interpreting a good, heavily project-oriented. In the consumer goods market—characterized by asymmetric information—the consumer is still required to make value judgments: the interpretation of a good may thus present itself as a collection of traits in view of an evaluation.

This search for clues involves inferential procedures that require abductive reasoning at different levels. The fact that some inferences, due to their apparent immediacy, seem almost ‘automatic’ should not lead us to forget that in the very tension of recognition there is already semiosis (Eco, 1990: 14) and that “the issue in the everyday practice of semiosis is to recognize a signifier as a signifier. And doing that requires a certain interpretive effort.” (ibid: 12)

If we admit the specificity of the “post-industrial object,” we believe this specificity does not lie—as some would claim—in its signic nature, but rather in the growing complexity of interpretive procedures that the subject must perform in making a judgment.

The coexistence, within the same culture, of different habits of valuation forces the consumer to constantly bet, depending on context and circumstance, on the adequacy of the judgment criteria.

That is why we believe scarcity, labor, or use-functions of a good should not be treated as intrinsic value-substances, but as semantic properties of the object actualized by the habits of valuation impressed on the subject.

Thus, the process of valuation is complex not only because of its inferential procedures, but also because the very adoption of a valuation habit, which conditions those procedures, is the result of a hypothesis and, as we will argue later, of an inner deliberation—that is, the outcome of an argumentative process.

Whereas identifying clues about a good’s rarity or the labor used to produce it requires the subject to activate conjectural mechanisms—e.g., inferring production information from physical features—the price already presents itself as a proposal of an axiological contract on the good’s value.

But this axiological contract is fiduciary in nature, and the relationship between price and value is not one of identity, but of semiotic reference. Price can be used to deceive, and “whenever there is a possibility of lying, we are dealing with a semiotic function” (Eco, 1975: 89).

We know that price is often interpreted as an indicator of value, and it is now well known that the circumstances and contexts determine its relevance for the evaluating subject.

However, similar analyses have not been conducted regarding other dominant habits of valuation and the interpretation of different properties as quality indicators.

We believe that semiotics can offer suitable tools for this. When we speak of “quality

indicators,” we refer to the pertinences through which a good is known and evaluated: any semantic property of the object—availability, use-functions, labor, or any other description—can be actualized.

In short, something is a quality indicator only when someone chooses to interpret it as such.

4. Individual Subject and Social Subject

The adoption of a habit of valuation implies the acceptance of a series of presumptions, which can vary in their level of generality. Choosing, for example, to orient one's value judgment based on the availability of a good means accepting the presumption that a commodity's value depends on its rarity. This is a presumption with a relatively high degree of generality.

However, with the pertinences and evaluative perspectives that the social subject considers shared, the individual evaluating subject finds himself comparing those with his own individual practices, which guide the selection of pertinent features and the attribution of value. This comparison, which takes on an argumentative form, may be marked by strong conflict.

We are well aware that disagreement between the individual subject and the social subject on values is far from uncommon: consider how the collective subject can sanction passions that result from flawed evaluations of objects. In any case, value is by definition the manifestation of a polarity: indeed, “every value judgment, while being an act of attribution, also contains a polemic aspect—namely, the rejection or acceptance of competing or allied attributions.” (Calabrese, 1987: 17)

Rather than maintaining a contrast between objective and subjective criteria of value, it is preferable to analyze the relationships between socially shared values and the values held by the individual subject.

5. Judgment as Deliberation

As we have seen, the issue of value is not only a matter of more or less intense interpretive tension, but also—above all—of the coexistence, within the same culture, of different habits of valuation.

The subject constructs hypotheses and must decide, each time, the parameter through which to know and evaluate a good.

Characterized by a regime of hypotheses and dialectical proofs, the cognitive process that leads to judgment is inherently argumentative. The evaluative act has little to do with evidence and necessity: we are, in fact, within the realm of the plausible and the probable.

A proper semantics should allow marketing theory to identify the selections made by the

arguments regarding the sememe that finds its manifestation in the specific product.

We believe the proposal of Stefano Traini (1994) for the description and construction of marketing strategies is, in light of our aims, one of the most convincing. The encyclopedic model he proposes should allow for the description of a semantic space susceptible to argumentative reorganizations.

However, we believe the strength of such a model depends on its ability to account for the syntactic form of value objects (cf. Greimas, 1991).

In our view, it is not crucial to identify the properties that govern “syntagmatic relations with other consumer objects” (Traini, 1994: 75), as is also proposed by the so-called syntagmatic approach to commodities (Kehret-Ward, 1987).

Instead, the real goal should be to analyze how the syntactic properties of the object represent a network of constraints on the subject’s evaluative path (cf. Greimas, 1991).

6. The Commercial Process

The arguments discussed also differ depending on the type of audience they address. In the case of inner deliberation, the audience consists of the subject himself, when he deliberates or reflects on the reasons for his actions (Perelman, 1958: 33).

But along the path from design and production to marketing, the product can be subjected to different valorizations. We must reasonably assume that the angles of pertinence through which a retailer and a potential consumer view the exchange object can differ greatly. The same divergence may exist—regarding the same object—between the retailer and the producer.

Moreover, it is likely that the same actor may assume different habits of valuation and adopt different arguments depending on the interlocutor: think, for example, of how the same product is presented by the same company to the consumer versus to the trade (e.g., commercial partners, wholesalers).

If we then imagine typical situations of longer distribution chains, we see other actors emerge—such as the sales agent or the dealer—for whom the argumentative process may take the form of a dialogue with a unique interlocutor (ibid.).

The multiplicity of audience types, arguments, and evaluative habits that populate the commercialization process should not discourage analysis; rather, it should stimulate the search for shared traits and for a metalanguage suitable for the various stages of the process.

Some argue (Grandi, 1992: 333) that “the plurality of marketing mix tools, that is, the physical diversity and the different communicative status of the media through which the product image is conveyed,” reveals “some of the limits of applying interpretive semiotics to

marketing problems.”

But if a semiotics of marketing is to be established, we believe it must begin precisely with questions that pertain to general semiotics, understood as a “reflection on the conditions of possibility of specific semiotics” (Eco, 1985: 331).

The first and ambitious objective that semiotics can aim for, in relation to the marketing object, is the same one that general semiotics once set for itself—namely, that “one can speak of superficially disparate phenomena in a unified manner” (ibid.).

This is why we insist so strongly on the hypothesis that the various phases of the commercialization process, although diverse in many aspects, might be characterized by a common inferential and argumentative procedure, regardless of the communication and representation subjects involved.

Even the analysis of advertising discourse, from the perspective we propose, should focus primarily on the pertinences shaped by the argumentative process, which remain, so to speak, available for future value investments.

Since “from a semiotic point of view, a product is an object constructed from a blend of properties in which every kind of information about it is included” (Pruni, 1994: 227), the question that advertising text analysis should answer is precisely the one Pruni poses in the case of car advertising:

“If a car is also made of descriptions, and since advertising is a description of the product, how does advertising determine the set of semantic properties that constitute the automobile?” (ibid.: 278)

7. Toward an Eccentric Marketing and a New Product Orientation

It has been rightly noted that marketing thought, characterized by “a pragmatic orientation,” presents itself as “a set of techniques, a performative practice whose privileged goal has been the increase of corporate sales.” (Codeluppi, 1993: 153)

But we must also keep in mind that this undeniable pragmatic vocation does not, in itself, distinguish marketing from other scientifically-oriented disciplines. A scientific practice should in fact allow, once its object is known, for programs aimed at modifying that very object. (Eco, 1985: 328)

We therefore merely observe that marketing theory is particularly concerned with programs of modification of its object. But it is clear that before attempting to intervene and modify or enhance its object, theory must first describe it.

The definition we offered in the first chapter—certainly incomplete—seemed nonetheless adequate to guide an initial description.

Let us now try to draw some consequences from the hypotheses we have posed and discussed, bearing in mind the pragmatic concerns of the marketing world.

Two ideas have implicitly guided our discussion:

1. The first stems from the hypothesis that the cognitive and evaluative procedures logically preceding the act of exchange can be described within a broad framework that assumes human decisions and actions are the outcomes of inferential processes. (Bonfantini, 1982: 113)
2. The second is that sememes are “effects of meaning independent from the semiosis that manifests them” (Marsciani & Zinna, 1991: 33). This means that the trajectory of meaning of the sememe could find contextual manifestation both in a lexeme of any natural language and in a drawing (ibid.). Just like a lexeme, the tradable good can be considered a complex configuration of virtual sememic traits, realized from time to time through interpretation.

The sememes themselves should not be viewed “as a collection of semes, the result of a pure combination,” as they often connect, implicitly, both actantial structures and thematic configurations (Greimas & Courtés, 1979: 309).

That is why we argue that marketing theory needs a semantics capable of accounting for the reorganization of semantic space operated by interpretive and argumentative practices.

Based on what we have discussed so far, we maintain that the encounter with semiotics should prompt the marketing world to pursue a new product orientation. This would mean translating strategic action into a systematic and preliminary investigation of the possible pertinences of the object.

In other words: we hypothesize and hope that one might begin from the syntactic organization of the object to make hypotheses about the practices that will guide its interpretation and valorization in later phases.

However, this kind of phenomenological return to the object can only be effective if placed within a theoretical framework that captures the complexity and eccentricity of the marketing object. And with the awareness that the marketing strategy itself must become eccentric.

Every description, every argumentation, and every value judgment that characterizes any stage of ideation, production, or commercialization contributes to the very definition of the exchange object.

The solid hierarchy of the phases in the commercialization process, assured by marketing strategy, dissolves into multiple decentralized decision areas. It is precisely the recognition of the eccentricity of the entire system that can allow marketing theory (and the semiotics of marketing) to focus on the crucial moments in the determination of value.

Value, after all, does not present itself to the subject as a self-evident truth, but rather as the provisional and convincing resolution of an argumentative process.

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